

HAWASSA UNIVERSITY INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY
CHEMICAL ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

Final Internship Report Paper

Hosting company: MoHA Soft Drinks Industry S.C Hawassa Millennium Pepsi cola Plant

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Prepared By: Hanna Tadesse

ID Number: Tech/0879/09

Company supervisor: Mr. Getaw G.

Advisor: Mr. Taresa M. (M.Sc)

Declaration

Hereby I declare that I, Hanna Tadesse, have authored independently this report writing for my internship with a topic “Report paper for an Internship at MoHA Soft Drinks Industry S.C.” and did not use any other means than indicated.

The parts of this work which have been taken in the wording or meaning of other works are indicated in each case with naming of the original reference.

Hanna Tadesse

Mr. Taresa M. (M.Sc.)

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Executive Summary

Internship is a great opportunity for an application of theoretical knowledge acquired at school to real solve real world problems in a business as well as human life there by enhancing ones' knowledge and practical skills.

This internship report paper first presents background history, organizational structure, main sections, products and services etc. about my internship host company, Hawassa MoHA Soft drink factory.

Then on the second part is my overall internship experience such as how I got into the company, my responsibilities and sections I have been working, my performance, challenges I have faced and the measures I have taken.

The third section of this report paper presents the benefits I have gained from my internship experience in terms of theoretical knowledge as well as practical skills.

On the fourth section of this paper material and energy balance on different rooms of the company is presented.

The fifth section of this paper contains challenges and problems of the company, case study, problem details, and solution for the problem, conclusion and recommendation for the company based on the case study.

The end this paper has reference to the original sources of materials which I have included into my report paper.

Acronyms

BH	bore hole
BOD	biological oxygen demand
CEO	chief executive officer
CIP	cleaning internal part / clean in place
COD	chemical oxygen demand
CSD	carbonated soft drink
EBI	empty bottle inspection
EDTA	ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid
FBI	full bottle inspection
FS	final syrup/ finished syrup
HACCP	hazard analysis critical control point
LPG	liquid petroleum gas
MEA	monoethanolamine (Ethanolamine)
MoHA	Mohammed Hussein AL-Amoudin
PET	positron - emission topography
PI	PepsiCo international
PPM	potassium per manganese
RGB	returnable glass bottle
RO	reverse osmosis
SWOT	strength, weakness, opportunities, and threats

Table of Content

Declaration	I
Acknowledgement	II
Executive Summary	III
Acronyms	IV
Table of Content	V
List of Tables	IX
List of Figures	X
1 Background of hosting company	1
1.1 Brief history about MoHA Industry S.C.	1
1.2 Brief History of Pepsi-Cola.....	1
1.3 The History of Pepsi Cola in Ethiopia	2
1.3.1 Nifas-Silk Pepsi cola Plant.....	2
1.3.2 Tekile-Haimanot Pepsi cola Plant.....	2
1.3.3 Gondar Pepsi cola plant	2
1.3.4 Dessie Pepsi cola plant.....	2
1.3.5 Hawassa Pepsi cola plant	2
1.4 Vision, Mission, Objectives and Values of MoHA.....	3
1.4.1 Vision.....	3
1.4.2 Mission.....	3
1.4.3 Objectives of MoHA.....	4
1.4.4 Core Values of MoHA	4
1.5 Organizational Structure and Workflow in MoHA.....	4
1.5.1 Organizational structure and management.....	4
1.5.2 Work flow in MoHA.....	6

1.6 Main sections inside the Hawassa plant	6
1.6.1 The Carbon Dioxide Plant	7
1.6.2 Syrup Preparation.....	13
1.6.3 Waste Water Treatment Plant	17
1.7 Main Products and Services	21
1.7.1 Main Products	21
1.7.2 Services	21
1.8 Customers and End-users of the product	21
1.9 Quality Control and Safety.....	21
1.10 Overall production process flow diagram	22
1.11 Production Inputs and Raw Materials for soft Drink	23
1.11.1 Power supply.....	23
1.11.2 Water Supply	23
1.11.3 Raw Materials	23
1.11.4 Human Resource.....	24
2 Overall Internship Experience	25
2.1 How I got into the company	25
2.2 Sections I have been working.....	25
2.3 Wok-flow in the sections.....	25
2.3.1 Water treatment section	25
2.3.2 Work flow in syrup preparation room	26
2.3.3 Bottle washer room	26
2.3.4 Filler room	27
2.3.5 Carbon dioxide preparation room	28
2.3.6 Compressor and chiller room.....	28

2.3.7	Quality control room/laboratory	29
2.3.8	Bottle washer	30
2.4	Tasks I have been executing.....	31
2.5	Procedures I used while executing my tasks.....	31
2.5.1	Quality of waste water	31
2.5.2	Analyzing the clarity of mix tank	31
2.6	My performance	32
2.7	Challenges	32
2.8	Measures.....	32
3	Benefits gained from the internship.....	33
3.1	Introduction.....	33
3.2	Practical Skills.....	33
3.3	Theoretical Knowledge	33
3.4	Interpersonal communication skills	33
3.5	Team work and Leadership skills.....	34
3.6	Work Ethic	34
3.7	Entrepreneurship skills.....	34
4	Material and Energy Balance.....	35
4.1	Material Balance	35
4.1.1	Balance on Pepsi Cola in Six Unit.....	35
4.1.2	Mass Balance for Mirinda Orange in Fourteen Unit	37
4.2	Energy Balance on Dissolving Tank.....	37
5	Case Study	39
5.1	List of problems observed at the company.....	39
5.2	List of solutions to the problems observed in the company	40

5.3 Case Study: Replacement of Organic Sugar by Artificial sweeteners	40
5.3.1 Sugar Substitutes (artificial sweeteners).....	41
5.3.2 Sweeteners that are safe to use.....	41
5.3.3 Comparison and Summary of artificial sweeteners	43
5.4 Methodology	44
5.4 Energy balance	44
5.5 Cost and energy analysis	46
5.5.1 Cost analysis	46
5.5.2 Energy analysis	46
5.6 Conclusions and recommendation on case study	47
5.6.1 Conclusion	47
5.6.2 Recommendation	47
Reference	i

List of Tables

Table 1: Ingredients for syrup for different soft drinks	14
Table 2: Main source of wastes in waste water treatment	18
Table 3: Human Resource Capital at MoHA	24
Table 4: Summary and comparison of sweeteners	43

List of Figures

Figure 1: Organizational structure of MoHA.....	5
Figure 2: Work flow in MoHA.....	6
Figure 3: Carbon Dioxide structure	7
Figure 4: Carbonated water.....	8
Figure 5: CO2 production process	12
Figure 6: Syrup production process	17
Figure 7: Waste water treatment flow diagram.....	20
Figure 8: Overall production process of MoHA.....	22
Figure 9: Raw Materials for Soft Drinks	23

1 Background of hosting company

1.1 Brief history about MoHA Industry S.C.

MoHA industry was born as a result of Ethiopian government's policy of privatization of government owned factories to stimulate the economy. Originally, MoHA was a chain of four factories known as Pepsi Cola stationed at Nifas-Silk and Tekile-Haimanot in Addis Ababa and other two more factories one in Gonder and the other in Dessie.

After sheik Mohammed Hussein A-Amoudin won the tender held by the Ethiopian Privatization Agency on 18th January 1996, those four Pesi-cola factories were privatized successfully and handed over on 4th April 1996. Hence the new company is named MoHA after **Mohammed Hussein A-Amoudin**.

1.2 Brief History of Pepsi-Cola

Pepsi was originally known as "Brad's Drink" after the name of the person Caleb Bradham who made it and sold it for the first time at his drug store in New Bern, North Carolina, United States, in 1893 [1].

Then the name of the drink was later changed to Pepsi-Cola after 5 years because it was advertised at that time to relive indigestion or an upset-stomach. The cola part of the name refers to the fact that it has a cola flavor, whereas the word Pepsi refers to an indigestion-easing beverage [1][2].

In 1903, Bradham expanded the bottling of Pepsi-Cola from his drugstore to a rented warehouse where he sold 7,968 gallons. The next year, Pepsi was sold in six-ounce bottles, and sales skyrocketed to 19,848 gallons [1][3].

Later in 1923, the Pepsi-Cola Company entered bankruptcy mainly because of losses incurred because the unpredictable sugar prices as a result of World War I. In 1931 president of candy manufacturing company in New York, known as Loft, Charles G. GUTH purchased Pepsi from the holding company.

In 1934, Charles G. Guth increased sales and popularity of Pepsi after the introduction of larger bottles (350ml) at a price of \$0.05 at that time a bottle worth about \$0.99 / 42 ETB on today's market [1].

1.3 The History of Pepsi Cola in Ethiopia

1.3.1 Nifas-Silk Pepsi cola Plant

Nifas-silk was the first Pepsi cola plant in Ethiopia, established in 1966 as Shared Company with an initial capital of birr 1 million.

The capacity of bottling line at that time was 20,000 bottles/hour. In 1986, the plant was renovated and expanded to a capacity of 50,000 bottles/hour with twin fillers. Total renovation and expansion investment cost estimated to birr 6,647,944.

1.3.2 Tekile-Haimanot Pepsi cola Plant

Tekile-Haimanot Pepsi cola plant was even older than Nifas-Silk plant. It was founded in 1961 as “Seba-Tej” Share Company but then it was evolved into a Pepsi cola factory after it was nationalized in 1975. Since 1978 it was producing Pepsi cola, Mirinda and other brands of various flavors.

1.3.3 Gondar Pepsi cola plant

Gondar Pepsi cola plant was private owned company before it was nationalized during the regime of Derg. It was producing “Wilk-Fite” water. But then after its nationalization it has started producing snap cola and snap orange.

1.3.4 Dessie Pepsi cola plant

Dessie plant was as well producing a different product, soda before 1979. Then later in 1979, it has stopped producing soda and started producing Pepsi cola, Miranda and cool carbonated water.

1.3.5 Hawassa Pepsi cola plant

The Hawassa plant is the newest MoHA soft drink chains and one of the seven soft drink plants under MoHA. Its foundation was laid in back in 1999 but it was completed after 8 years in 2007. Then it was launched during the Ethiopian millennium, in 2008 G.C, hence named Hawassa millennium Pepsi cola plant.

It is located at the southeast edge of Hawassa town on 25,000 square meter adjacent to textile and Hawassa cheap wood factory.

The plant has a state of the art technology. For instance, it includes a reverse osmosis water treatment plant and infrared bottle inspection technology. The high tech facility has the highest yield as well with a production capacity of 36,000 bottles per hour and hence it costed highest total capital investment about Birr 180 million.

It was targeted to cover the demand of soft drinks of the whole Southern Nations, Nationalities and People region (SNNPR) there by minimization of transportation cost of soft drinks and better deliver-ability. The plant is eco-friendly. It has its own waste water treatment plant and releases only filtered and neutral water back to the environment.

1.4 Vision, Mission, Objectives and Values of MoHA

1.4.1 Vision

MoHA's vision is to make each Pepsi product to be a drink of first choice among consumers, to expand the market share and fully satisfy the demand for soft drinks in the country. It strives to create superior value for the shareholders, customers as well as employees.

1.4.2 Mission

MoHA's mission is to be the best beverage industry in the country. To achieve that, it is continuously improving on addressing the needs and concerns of customers, employees, shareholders and local communities.

Promotion of employees, an emphasis on cost efficiency, market expansion and profitability is also being worked on to achieve the company's mission.

Furthermore, MoHA would like to keep expanding its market share by focusing on innovation and technological improvement to stay ahead of the game.

1.4.3 Objectives of MoHA

General objective

The general objective of MoHA soft drinks industry S.C. is to become a successful business venture by evaluating various business strategies.

Specific Objectives

The specific objectives of MoHA are:

- To produce, distribute and sell beverage, bottle, as well as inputs like Carbon dioxide.
- To invest in other business enterprises.
- To promote employees and increase job satisfaction.

1.4.4 Core Values of MoHA

Core values of MoHA Industry are:

- Customer satisfaction.
- Enhancement of positive corporate identity and image.
- Ensure employees empowerment.
- Be committed to social responsibilities.
- Sustainability of quality and excellence.
- Team work.

1.5 Organizational Structure and Workflow in MoHA

1.5.1 Organizational structure and management

Board of directors are selected from shareholders of the company by majority vote and are responsible for presenting the concerns and interests of shareholders and the company. The board of directors appoints a chief executive officer who will be directly in contact with each department managers in the company.

MoHA operates with a Head office located at Addis Ababa led by a chief executive officer (CEO). Hierarchically, the CEO is accountable to the chairman of the board.

Figure 1: Organizational structure of MoHA

1.5.2 Work flow in MoHA

Figure 2: Work flow in MoHA

1.6 Main sections inside the Hawassa plant

At the Hawassa MoHA soft drink industry, there are 8 main production rooms each with its own quality control room, and ingredients /raw materials room for the production of soft drink.

These rooms are:

- 1) Water treatment room.
- 2) Syrup room.
- 3) Bottle washer room.
- 4) Filler room.
- 5) CO₂ Plant.
- 6) Boiler room.
- 7) Chiller room.
- 8) Waste water treatment plant and Laboratory room.

At the Hawassa MoHA, there two plants with in the main plant.

These are:

- CO₂ plant and
- Water treatment plant.

They are modular plants, they can operate independently aside from the main soft drink plant. This is because production of CO₂ and water treatment is not only used in soft drink manufacturing process but they can be used for other productions as an input ingredients. For example, the Water treatment plant can serve treatment of water for a drinking purpose, washing, boiling & other purposes.

1.6.1 The Carbon Dioxide Plant

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is acidic colorless gas with a density around 53% higher than dry air. It occurs naturally in Earth's atmosphere as a trace gas with a concentration of about 0.04% (412 ppm) by volume [12].

Natural sources of CO₂ are volcanoes, hot springs, and carbonate rocks. Because of its solubility in water, CO₂ also occurs naturally in groundwater, rivers, lakes, seawater as well as ice caps [12].

Figure 3: Carbon Dioxide structure

Carbon dioxide in soft drinks

Carbon dioxide is an element that gives carbonated soft drinks a sparkling behavior. Traditionally, the carbonation of beer and sparkling wine came about through natural fermentation, but many

manufacturers carbonate these drinks with carbon dioxide recovered from the fermentation process [12].

Figure 4: Carbonated water

Advantages of adding carbon dioxide in soft drinks

- It enhances both the beverages taste and eye appeal due to its sparkling effect.
- It does adds a sanitary protection & greater shelf life.
- It contributes to the production process itself by displacing air from water and product during processing, supplying counter pressure needs for some filler bowl & displacing air from the filled can head space just prior to seaming syrup preparation.

Production of Carbon dioxide

Carbon dioxide can be obtained by distillation of air, but that method is inefficient. One way to produce carbon dioxide is by combustion of all carbon-based fuels, such as, methane (natural gas), gasoline, diesel, kerosene, propane, coal, wood and other generic organic matters. For example, the chemical reaction between methane and oxygen can produce CO₂ [12].

Carbon dioxide can also be produced by heating/ calcining a limestone (CaCO₃) at about 850 °C which produces calcium oxide/ quicklime (CaO) and carbon dioxide.

Main raw materials used CO₂ Production:

- Fuel gas (naphtha)
- Soda ash (sodium carbonates)

- MEA (mono ethylene amine)
- Freon gas
- PPM (potassium per manganese)
- Anti-foam

Sections of the CO₂ Plant

- Generating section
- Separating section
- Purification section
- Storage unit

Main operational units of the CO₂ production plant

The main production units of the CO₂ plant are:

1. Burner

The burner generates CO₂ by combustion of fuel oil. The fuel oil is sucked from the fuel tanker by means of an oil pump. The temperature used for separation of the fuel gases is 230 °C -360 °C range.

Burner has two parts, the first part is used to break down of the bond of fuel gas to form light fuel gasses and the other one is used to boil MEA, soda ash, & water in the MEA tanker.

2. Fuel gas scrubber

In this unit a fuel gas generated from the burner is washed by soft water that comes from the softener to cool down the fuel gas. Moreover, toxic gases like sulfur dioxide is removed from the gas by the presence of soda ash in the water. Then sulfur dioxide containing water is sent to the water treatment section for treatment before the water is released into the environment.

3. Absorber

The absorber is designed to separate CO₂ from the softened fuel gas from the previous step the aid of solvent absorbent known as monoethanolamine (MEA or Ethanolamine) at moderate

temperature and high pressure. In this unit the CO₂ gas is absorbed by the help of MEA and the leftover gas is released to the surrounding atmosphere because it has not any significant effect on the environment or life. The operation temperature for the absorbers is between 34 °C - 38 °C.

4. Stripper

Stripper works by a reverse principle of absorber because absorber is working absorb CO₂ where as a stripper works to lose CO₂ at high temperature 108 °C. The absorbed gas by the agent of MEA and some amount of soda ash must be separated by using stripper to obtain a more pure carbon dioxide. The stripper operates between 70 °C to 90°C in order to break the bond between MEA and CO₂ gas.

5. Heat exchanger

The heat exchanger, also known as a gas cooler, is used to cool down the CO₂ gas. Since the stripper uses heat to separate CO₂ and MEA, cooling of the CO₂ is required to reduce temperature of the CO₂ gas from 90 °C to 40 °C before the gas is passed to for further processing.

6. Water Separator

When passed through the heat exchanger, the CO₂ gas might absorb some moisture. Therefore a water separator separates the moisture from the gas. In this section the separation is done by the gravity difference. The CO₂ gas has light density compared with water, hence it will float up and the moisture will sink below and it will be sent to the MEA tanker.

7. PPM Scrubber

In the PPM scrubber, the CO₂ gas is further more purified and cooled by using potassium per manganese. The potassium per manganese will absorb the extra gases, impurities and heat. In this section the temperature reduces down to 20 °C.

8. Compressor

The compressor is has two tubes. These are inner and after cooler. In these two tubes CO₂ will be pressurized with 9-12 bar at the section point and temperature of 20 °C. It has two stages with a different pressure range. The first stage has a pressure of 65-70 bar and second stage has a pressure of 250-270 bar. Finally, at the discharge section it is pressurized to 600-900 bars.

9. Dehydrator

Although cooler has removed moisture from the CO₂ gas in intermediate and after cooler, it still might have some amount of water or moisture. Therefore, the dehydrator will further dry the gas using its vessels filled with molecular sieves.

10. Activated Carbon filter

The carbon filter is used to remove undesired odor, moisture and other impurities from the gas. Traces of different organic and Sulphur compounds can be trapped in this section.

11. Condenser

The gas from the filter unit finally goes in to the condenser. The condenser is a heat exchanger where CO₂ further cooled using a refrigerant. The Freon gas is a refrigerant that is used for solidifying the carbon dioxide gas [13]. The aim of solidifying the CO₂ gas is for minimizing storage space and cost. The solid CO₂ gas will then be stored in a tank, which can store up to 21,000 Kg of solid CO₂ gas.

Figure 5: CO₂ production process

1.6.2 Syrup Preparation

Syrup is a thick, viscous liquid that consists mainly a solution of sugar in water. It is a sweetener that is added to soft drinks to give a sweet taste. It contains a large amount of dissolved sugar as well as sugar crystals. Its consistency is similar to molasses. Its viscosity is due to the multiple hydrogen bonds between the dissolved sugars, which has many hydroxyl (OH) groups [14].

Syrups can be made by dissolving sugar in water or by reducing naturally sweet juices such as cane juice, sorghum juice, maple sap or agave nectar. Corn syrup is made from corn starch using an enzymatic process that converts it to sugars [14].

In Hawassa MoHA soft drink factory, preparation of syrup takes place in a syrup room which at the heart of the soft drink plant. Generally, there are two types of syrup: simple syrup and finished syrup.

Simple Syrup

Simple syrup (aka sugar syrup, or bar syrup) is a basic sugar-and-water syrup that is made by stirring granulated sugar into hot, but not boiling, water until the sugar is dissolved and then cooling the solution. This results in a clear syrup 1+1/2 the quantity of the original measure of sugar or water. The sugar is kept at a specific temperature during the process, typically below 320 °F (160 °C)[14].

Finished syrup (Flavored syrup)

Flavored syrups are made by infusing simple syrups with flavoring ingredients. A wide variety of flavors can be used, often in combination with each other, such as herbs, spices, or aromatics. For example, *syrupus aromaticus* is prepared by adding certain quantities of orange flavor and cinnamon water to simple syrup [14].

Ingredients used for syrup preparation

- Water
- Celatom (clears the water)
- Refined sugar

- Flavors
- Other dry ingredients such as sodium benzoate, sunset yellow, citric acid anhydrous, potassium sulfate, sodium chloride mainly, etc. mainly depending up on a type of soft drink.

Table 1: Ingredients for syrup for different soft drinks

Soft-Drink	Dry ingredients
Mirinda	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sodium benzoate • potassium sulfate • Sodium chloride • citric acid • sunset yellow
Pepsi	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pepsi acidulents
7up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sodium benzoate • sodium citrate dehydrated • citric acid anhydrous • sodium citrate
Mirinda apple	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sodium benzoate • sodium citrate, • citric acid
Mirinda tonic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sodium benzoate, • citric acid anhydrous
Mirinda pine-apple	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • sodium benzoate, • potassium sulfate, • Sodium chloride • citric acid, • Tetrizzini sunset yellow

Syrup preparation steps

1st Water is pumped into a tank.

2nd heat is applied from the boiler on the tank at the desired level for different beverage with different volume. But typically at a temperature of 80°C and 3 bar. The main reason for heating is to kill the microorganisms that come with sugar and to dissolve the sugar.

3rd desired amount of granular sugar is added by using a conveyor belt in to the hot at 80°C water in the tank and then the tank will be agitated for 20-25 min. The conveyor contains strainer to prevent the passage of fiber and physically detectable matter.

4th activated carbon will be added into the tank for purification purpose. The activated carbon acts as a bleaching agent and keep agitating for another 20 minutes.

5th Hyflo, filtration agent, will be added again and agitated for five more minutes.

6th The dissolved sugar moves to a horizontal filter, which is used to filter fine particles that might be present in the dissolved sugar.

7th Dissolved sugar solution is sent to filter tank. At this tank 2.82 kg provided from store room can be added in to filter tank to prepare celatom cake in the filter tank for the purpose of filtering syrup that can be prepared in the dissolving tank. At this section the syrup can be filtered by overflowing it on the cake prepared. In this filter tank there are 37 plates that are filled by celatom cake for filtration process and finally pure syrup can be obtained. After this process the filtered syrup transferred into buffer tank.

8th A buffer tank is typically used when there is a variable cooling requirement. In such applications the tank is used as storage to cover peak loads or in situations when a surge in demand exceeds the capacity of the cooling system. A buffer tank is well-suited to situations where cooling loads are small because it reduces the number of starts and thus decreases wear and energy consumption. This tank has upper and lower sensor, which used to for protect over flow and incoming dissolved sugar respectively.

9th Dissolved sugar moves to police filter. At this section the impurities remained from filter tank can be filtered with help of police filter bag. This process helps in preventing the impurities that can be in the syrup with the help of this filtering bag allowing only the passage of pure syrup.

10th Filtered sugar syrup can be flown in to a plate heat exchanger to cool syrup 15 °C - 24°C. The aim of removing heat from simple syrup is to produce cooled flavored syrup juice that can be used for soft drink production.

11th After production of simple syrup from the above steps its brix must be 62.7 and it can be checked by chemists before producing final syrup. Final syrup can be produced by using concentrate tank and mix tanks. At concentrate tank the flavor and different chemicals like sodium chloride, sodium benzoate, potassium sulfate, citric acid and others can be added and the volume of the tank is 450Lt.

12th Finally the syrup prepared at the above steps can be entered in to mixing tank for the purpose of mixing the flavor and color produced at concentrate tank and to produce final syrup by adding water at this tank and its brix can be 51. This can also be checked by chemists.

Finally, the flavored and colored syrup can be prepared to produce soft drink by adding carbon dioxide at the filler. In syrup room Mirinda orange, Pepsi cola, Mirinda tonic, Mirinda brown apple, Mirinda pineapple, and 7up are produced. Each type of soft drink is produced in its own unit.

Figure 6: Syrup production process

The flavored and colored syrup can be used to produce soft drinks by adding carbon dioxide at the filler. In the syrup room Mirinda orange, Pepsi cola, Mirinda tonic, Mirinda brown apple, Mirinda pineapple, and 7up are produced.

1.6.3 Waste Water Treatment Plant

Waste water is produced as a byproduct from industrial, commercial or agricultural activities and it contains pollutants with a varying level depending on its source. Because of that, a waste water has negative impact on the environment and human life.

The production of soft drinks typically pollutes water with sugar and other easily biodegradable substances. Waste water from a soft drink consists of waste ingredients from soft drinks, syrup, detergents from the washing of bottles, lubricants used in the machinery, etc.

Table 2: Main source of wastes in waste water treatment

Area	Contribution
Water treatment plant	Inorganic –water treatment chemicals, solids
Syrup room	Cleaning chemicals, sucrose, flavor
Bottle washer	Caustic and other cleaning chemicals, solids
Bottling	Solids, sucrose, flavor

Water Treatment methods

Biological water treatment is the most common method used for treatment of soft drink waste water because soft drink waste water has a lot of organic content.

A complete biological treatment includes optional screening, neutralization equalization, anaerobic and aerobic treatment, sludge separation (e.g. sedimentation, or dissolved air floatation) and sludge disposal.

Chemical and physical treatment processes like coagulation, sedimentation or floatation are occasionally used to reduce the organic content before the waste water enters the biological treatment process.

Steps in Waste Water Treatment Plant

1st the waste water comes from different station of the plants by means of gravity and enters into preliminary treatment station. This station contains three chambers, these three chambers mainly are used for physical treatment of the waste water. As the waste water enters in the screening chamber, large sized oil, grease, sticks, and floating materials will be removed.

Then the PH of the waste water will be measured to know the acidity to know whether a neutralizing agent should be used agent. Then if the waste water has a PH value greater than 8.5 or less than 6.5 PH value, it will be further treated by using neutralizing agents.

2nd the waste water will be sent to a collection tank. It can be stored there up to 8 hours. The purpose of this tank is for sedimentation of solids and balance supplying to next treatment process.

3rd the waste water will be sent the primary treatment chamber. This chamber like preliminary chamber has different sections. The first section is a reaction chamber where sulfuric acid added to lowering the PH value to seven and to make the bond between suspended particles brittle.

4th the neutralized waste water moves to coagulator tank where the particles that are found in the waste water will be coagulated by using flocculent agent called poly electrolyte.

5th the coagulated particles removed by settling tanker one by their gravity. Then the settled waste water moves to bioreactor tank. Sugar bacteria by nature could be very dangerous when released to the environment.

6th the chlorinated water moves to sand filter for trap the high flow particles plus chlorine. Then the purified water will be sent to treated water tank. After that the treated water will be released into the Cheffe River.

Flow diagram of waste water treatment

Figure 7: Waste water treatment flow diagram

1.7 Main Products and Services

1.7.1 Main Products

Hawassa MoHA produces six major Pepsi brands. These are:

- 1) Pepsi
- 2) Mirinda Orange
- 3) Mirinda Tonic
- 4) Mirinda Apple
- 5) Mirinda Pine Apple and
- 6) 7-up

To produce these products, MoHA has a got a franchised license from International Pepsi Cola Company which controls the quality of the products based on the parent company standard.

1.7.2 Services

In addition to producing the soft drinks, the Hawassa plant also produces a CO₂ gas as well for the company's beverage production purpose. Depending on the amount of production, the surplus production of CO₂ can be sold for external consumers who use it for food preservation purpose.

1.8 Customers and End-users of the product

Primary customers of the soft drinks produced at Hawassa branch are mainly the people in the South Nations, Nationalities and People Region (SNNPR). Main customers, for example, are from populated towns in the south region such as Hawassa, Hossana, Arbaminch, Dilla, etc.

In addition to those regions, customers in some parts of Oromia region like Shashemene, Zeway, Meki, Borena, Bale, etc. are also end-users of the product.

1.9 Quality Control and Safety

For the quality of the product all factory workers are responsible but more specifically there are people assigned a quality assurance task.

These are:

- Quality control room worker
- Pepsi Cola unknown quality checker

In addition to the responsible workers, the quality of the products is also being monitored by the Ethiopia food & drug controlling authority as well as international quality assurance institutions like Hazard analysis critical control point (HACCP) and the American international bottling (AIB).

MOHA has also received PepsiCo-AIB award (Quality Excellence award) for its food Safety, Quality and Environmental Management Systems.

The plant has also clinic and Medical facility equipped with the necessary medical equipment and professional health personnel. It also has hygienic toilets and wash room facilities are available that can accommodate all employees and as well as guests.

1.10 Overall production process flow diagram

Figure 8: Overall production process of MoHA

1.11 Production Inputs and Raw Materials for soft Drink

1.11.1 Power supply

The plant has its own generator (1000 Kw) alternative for electric power (EELPA), fuel station, and engineering services like mechanical work shop, electrical work shop, and automotive work shop including car wash services.

1.11.2 Water Supply

Water is supplied from own bore holes located in the plant premises that are constructed based on the well head protection program having a total capacity of 21.4 liter/sec which satisfies the current demand for plant operation.

1.11.3 Raw Materials

Water is 90% of the raw material needed for production of soft-drinks followed by 10% of cane sugar sourced from local industries and concentrates. Dry components and concentrate flavors are the main ingredients used for syrup additives enhancing a characteristics taste for the unique product and are supplied from Pepsi Cola international.

Figure 9: Row Materials for Soft Drinks

1.11.4 Human Resource

Currently the plant employed about 600 employees of whom 395 are male and 119 are females.

Table 3: Human Resource Capital at MoHA

employee	Sex	Number of employee
Permanent	Male	600
	Female	395
Contract	Male	3
	Female	3
Total	Both	600

2 Overall Internship Experience

2.1 How I got into the company

At the Hawassa University, students who have completed third year second semester chemical Engineering courses, start doing their internship at Industries so that they can practice their school knowledge at the Industry. The University gives students an authorization letter so that they can apply for an Internship based on their expertise and field of study.

Once I received my authorization letter, I started looking for companies mainly in Hossana, Hawassa and Addis Ababa. After some searching and communication I was accepted to do my internship, on March 10th, at the MoHA soft drinks industry Hawassa millennium Pepsi cola plant and the started working there.

2.2 Sections I have been working

During my internship session, I have been engaging actively in the nine main sections of Hawassa millennium Pepsi cola plant. These are: -

- Water treatment section
- Syrup preparation section
- Bottle washer section
- Filler and packaging section
- Carbon dioxide production plant
- Compressor and chiller plant
- Quality control room
- Steam generation plant
- Waste water treatment section

2.3 Wok-flow in the sections

2.3.1 Water treatment section

Water is the major ingredient in soft drink manufacturing process. Water treatment is the removing process of toxic chemicals, biological contaminants, suspended solids & additional gasses from underground well water. The main goals of water treatment process in soft drink production is to

produce water fit for process production & cleaning purposes. The water treatment process uses different purification methods including physical purification process like filtration & sedimentation, biological purification processes like slow sand filter or biologically active carbon and chemical purification process including chlorination & use of electromagnetic radiation (UV).

Treating water reduces the concentration of particulate matter including suspended particles, parasites, bacteria, algae, viruses, and fungi as well as it reduces the concentration of dissolved & particulate matter. In addition to this deep well water also have a tendency to pick up minerals & salts from underground through which water passes. Therefore, to achieve the water quality which is prescribed by the factory we need to give additional treatment to the incoming water, which will be used to manufacture syrup and beverage.

2.3.2 Work flow in syrup preparation room

A syrup is a thick, viscous liquid consisting sugar solution in water, containing a large amount of dissolved sugar but showing little tendency to deposit crystals. The preparation of syrup process takes place in a syrup room which also called the heart of the soft drink plant. Generally, syrup divided in to two: simple syrup and finished syrup.

Simple syrup is the solution of water and granular sugar dissolved in the dissolve tank and purified by using different purification system. While the flavor and dry components are added and agitated at recommended content, the simple syrup is going to be said finished syrup.

Finished syrup is the mixture of simple syrup, flavors and dry components. Each type of beverage has its own aging time before going to be filled to enhance the flavor oil of the syrup which depends on the Pepsi cola standard.

2.3.3 Bottle washer room

One of the most important processes in soft drink production is bottle washing. The high quality of the product depends up on how thoroughly the bottles are cleaned immediately before filling. The bottling process starts with the passing of the returnable bottles through a wash and rinse sequence. Then, the cleaned bottles are carefully inspected before they go automatically through consecutive steps of filling, crowning, mixing, labeling, packaging and shipping.

Bottle washing consists of soaking or flushing the bottles with caustic soda solution, sometimes combined with other cleansing agents such as soda ash, sodium aluminate, or tri sodium phosphate. The bottles are then scrubbed both inside and out before they are rinsed with potable water.

The bottle-washing equipment classified into three types this are:- soaker washers, brush washers and hydro washers. The bottles enter the washer through an automatic loader which handles the bottles separately from each other. Then, they get a pre-rinse before they enter a series of soaking compartments containing caustic solutions at a specific temperature.

After the bottles go through final rinsing, they are discharged from the washer in a gentle motion and placed in an upright position for further visual inspection. The washing solutions will gradually lose its caustic strength as the washing process progresses. Reaction with impurities depletes the NaOH in solution therefore; there is a need to check the causticity periodically so that the caustic concentration may be adjusted as required.

2.3.4 Filler room

It is one of the production sections whose purpose is to verify that container is consistently filled to the correct level as established by correct volume or weight for brand and package type. There are 5 main machines to do the entire job under filling room. These are:- EBI machine, Mixer machine, Filler machine, Crown machine, Date coder & Packer machine. In the filling process the filler follows six main steps to fill each bottles, these are:-

Evacuation: - is used only on rigid container, where the container is subjected to a vacuum remove 90% of the air content before pressurizing with gas. This is a significant process when filling particularly oxygen sensitive beverages as the step can be repeated after pressurizing with gas, thus removing 90% of mixed gas, leaving a highly concentrated gas atmosphere in the container.

Rinsing: - clean the bottle by using flushing with carbon dioxide.

Pressurized with gas: - is carried out after the container is sealed to the filling valve. Gases from the filler ring bowl flows in to the container until both pressures are the same.

Filling: - When the filling valve opens and beverage flows over a vent tube in to the container.

Filling level correction: - is important for filling level accuracy.

Sniffting: - Serve to gently lower the pressure in the container and allow the beverage to settle to prevent fobbing of the beverage as it is lowered from the filling valve. Foaming problem in filling processes may cause problem on product quality, economy and operation system.

2.3.5 Carbon dioxide preparation room

Carbon dioxide gas can be produced by using fuel gas or naphtha (liquid in nature) as a raw material. In addition to this for the production of CO₂ gas there are different chemical agents that added in different section for cleaning (separating), absorbing & clarifying purpose here are:- soda ash, MEA, Freon gas, PPM, anti-foam & gas oil. The all over process of the preparation has four main sections this are:- generating section, separating section, purification section & Storage unit.

2.3.6 Compressor and chiller room

Chiller room is one of the rooms in the plant which is responsible for cooling. Basically beverage industries require certain amount of cold temperature for healthy product to be produced. So chiller is very important to keep this requirement. Those things to be cooled includes simple syrup in the syrup room, finished syrup in the filler room and cold water used in bottle washer section. There are two refrigerants in the chiller, these are ammonia and glycol. Since ammonia is toxic chemical it is not directly contacted with the fluid which is going to be cooled but it exchanges heat with the glycol, which has no toxicity.

Compressor room is a room which is responsible for the supply of dry air which is used in the pneumatic system. For the continuing performance of control systems and working elements it is inevitable to guaranty whether the air supply is at required pressure, dryness and cleanness. If these conditions are not fulfilled certain term regeneration of the system will occur. The effect of downtime on the machinery in addition to increased cost of repair and replacement of parts is one of the biggest issues in the industrial management. So this is the room where we make sure quality air processing is done. The raw materials used in this room are atmospheric air and oil. The final product is dry and clean air suitable for the pneumatic system.

2.3.7 Quality control room/laboratory

The quality control room in this plant is sub divided in to two main sections. These are physio-chemical room & micro-biological room.

Physio - Chemical Room:- In this section mostly foreign material are checked & observed, PH values, alkalinity, the amount of brix in the simple and final syrup, purity of carbon dioxide, etc. In addition to this by preparing a sample taken from raw materials and chemicals before it input to determine its color, odor, acidity, basicity, physical or chemical property, etc. Areas where sample preparation includes: -

1. Water Treatment:- By taking sample from three sampling area (raw water, soft water, treated water) to determine the main parameters within 4 hours. These parameters mainly include:

- i. **PH value:** - in this case the given sample of water checks its PH value by using PH meter. The required PH value of each section of water is to be 7.
- ii. **Conductivity:** - is measure the presence of mineral concentration in the water. Depending on the result the correction will be taken based on its result range.
- iii. **Alkalinity:** - is a measure of the capacity of water to neutralize acid by using (0.02N).
- iv. **Turbidity:** - it is also measure the coldness or haziness of the water & it is caused by the presence of non-sucrose substances like suspended minerals (ash), polysaccharides, and high molecular weight poly phenol.
- v. **Total hardness:** - by using EDTA (0.01 N) chemical to detect the presence of calcium & magnesium containing minerals such as dolomite, lime stone & chalk in the water.

2. Simple and Final Syrup: During the product production process the following parameter will be controlled: -

- i. **Brix:** - it measures the sugar content or total solids found in the syrup.
- ii. **Color:** - by using either spectrometer or observing by eye the color of syrup will be checked. The color tells weather the syrup is filtered properly or not.
- iii. **Percent of ash:** - is measure the quality of the sugar by boiling the sugar in water bath & measure its quality (absorption) by UV spectra-photo meter.

iv. **Titrateable acid:** - which tell whether the sample has acidic property or not, unwanted substances or if the dry components did not add correctly or it form aging.

3. Line or Final product:-In this case by taking line or final products within 20 min the following will be checked:- The presence of foreign materials, Cork size, fill height, & fill height gape, The temperature, pressure, brix, density & carbon dioxide content of the products, Production time, gross weight, TOA, date coding

4. Ingredient & Carbon-dioxide:-The ingredient & carbon dioxide before it mixes within the process; the purity, physical or chemical property must be controlled. In case of testing the purity of carbon dioxide the following equipment will be used: -

- i. Carbon dioxide liquid injection unit: - used to convert the solid carbon dioxide to gas phase.
- ii. Tube sulfur analysis: - used to measure the content of sulfur amount in the gas.
- iii. Detective tube measuring: - used to determine the presence of other gases in the carbon dioxide gas

2.3.8 Bottle washer

In this case the amount of caustic soda, its strength & free EDTA detected at this section by using HCl (1N), (2.5 N), (0.01 N) respectively.

i. Steam generation plant/boiler room

Boiler is a closed vessel in which water is converted into steam with the application of heat. Boiler room is an auxiliary room which is important for different purposes like syrup dilution, bottle and crate washer. This room is basically responsible to produce hot water. The raw materials used to produce the required heat includes: - soft water from water treatment, light oil (for startup) and LPG gas for the spark. The capacity of this boiler to produce steam is 3500 kg/hrs at 185°C.

ii. Water treatment plant

Waste water is used water from any combination of domestic, industrial, commercial or agricultural activities. Waste water generally contains a large number of physical, chemical, &

biological pollutants at varying concentration levels. Industrial waste water is produced by industrial activity which includes any material that is rendered unusable during a manufacturing process such as: - soft drink plant. The production of soft drinks typically pollutes the process water with sugar & other easily biodegradable substances. The waste water of soft drink consists of wasted soft drinks & syrup water from the washing of bottles which contain detergents & caustic & finally lubricants used in the machinery.

2.4 Tasks I have been executing

During my internship at MOHA soft drinks industry Hawassa plant, I have been performing some duties. The work piece or lists of tasks I have been executing were:

- ✓ Measuring the quality of waste water before and after treatment.
- ✓ Analyzing the clarity of mix tank before using for another brand.
- ✓ Measuring the amount of brix, CO₂ content of the finished product.

2.5 Procedures I used while executing my tasks

2.5.1 Quality of waste water

The main parameters to measure the quality of waste water before treatment are PH value, Temperature, TDS, BOD and COD. Based on the result we will select chemicals to treat the effluent. Then after treatment the temperature and the PH is measured before releasing to the environment. The standard temperature is less than 40°C and the PH must be between 6 and 9.

2.5.2 Analyzing the clarity of mix tank

After performing CIP we have to make sure that our mix tank is clean, sanitized and free from micro-organisms. In order to check its clarity we will take a sample (final rinse water) from the internal part of the mix tank and we will remove the water by using membrane filtration technique which lets the micro-organism to retain on the surface of the membrane.

Then we will add a media to grow micro-organisms and put the sample in the incubator (total aerobic bacteria incubator, coliform bacteria incubator, yeast mold and mold incubator) then we will set the temperature of the incubator, and duration of the sample staying in it.

(for coliform bacteria 34°C-36°C for 24 hours, for total aerobic bacteria 34°C-36°C for 48-51 hours and for yeast or mould 24°C-26°C for 117-123 hours) then we will count the micro-organisms by using colony counter. If the amount of micro-organisms is less than the maximum standard, the mix tank is safe to use, rather further CIP is performed.

2.6 My performance

During the three months of work, as an intern, at MOHA Hawassa plant, overall I could say I had a great learning and performance experience. I have performed tasks assigned to me successfully, as well as I had a great communication with my colleagues and my supervisor.

2.7 Challenges

Here are a list of challenges I have faced at my work:

- The temperature difference in some rooms was very difficult to adapt for me. For example, the syrup preparation room, filler room, boiler room and bottle washer room were very hot but in contrast flavor storage room, and chiller and compressor room were very colder. As I go from one room to another while at work, my body struggled to adapt with the variance of temperature in each room.
- A bad smell from the waste treatment plant was very hard to handle. Especially in the afternoon it gets worse and was giving me a running nose.
- The other challenge I faced is loud noise from the machines. Not only it hard on ears and it was also was making communicating harder with co-workers. The company should consider giving ear safety headsets for people who work in the noisy sections of the plant.

2.8 Measures

To overcome the challenges I have taken some measures listed below:

- Using moderate outfits for the hot or cold environment based on the section I am working.
- Using extra masks to minimize the bad smell from the waste water treatment plant.
- Using ear plugs to avoid ear damage by high sound waves from the factory or if the sound is high and disturbing, opening mouth to minimize ear drum damage.

3 Benefits gained from the internship

3.1 Introduction

From my internship, I have obtained a lot of benefits in terms practical skills, theoretical knowledge, improving communication skills, work ethic, leadership as well as entrepreneurial skills which are described below in more detail.

3.2 Practical Skills

Working as an intern at MOHA helped me to learn a lot of practical skills that are required to become a professional chemical engineer. I have learned a lot about how companies in the real world operate to produce a product and drive a profit.

I was able to see and understand how theoretical knowledge and practical skills can be combined to run a manufacturing plants like MOHA. I also learned that manufacturing industries are really interdisciplinary. I have seen people from different academic background and level working together, sharing knowledge and experience.

3.3 Theoretical Knowledge

During my internship, I had more opportunity to read and learn how soft drinks are manufactured by having a dialogue and asking questions the professionals who work there. I also had an opportunity to refer to some documentations at the factory which boosted my theoretical knowledge.

3.4 Interpersonal communication skills

This internship was a good opportunity for me to develop my communication and interpersonal skills. I learned how to communicate better with co-workers in a professional and formal way as well as a non-formal friendly way out of the work context on tea breaks.

I have also learned how to communicate in writing by e-mail when I was searching for my internship place. That experience helped me to learn how to write a professional and clear message by e-mail.

Therefore, my Internship experience taught me that communication skill is important skill to become an outstanding professional and excel in one's career.

3.5 Team work and Leadership skills

Team work is much better than individual work. Teams that know how to collaborate and work together will always archive a great result. Because of this I was always trying to be a good team player and good leader for the tasks I was given to execute.

Though I was not given a direct leadership role, I have observed the role of team leaders and supervisors in improving the team's performance, effectiveness and efficiency.

3.6 Work Ethic

Work ethics is being personally accountable and responsible for work that someone does. Work ethics involves attitude, behavior, communication and interaction with others. It is also being respectful and accepting ideas from others.

Personally, my internship taught me a lot about work ethic. I learned how to be punctual, how to follow the company's rules and regulations, and how to fulfil my duties as an intern.

3.7 Entrepreneurship skills

Entrepreneurship is one of the most important skills for any professional. I have understood that one person can become entrepreneur if he/she a skill, knowledge, a strong work ethic and risk taking behavior.

I have learned a lot about how entrepreneurs add a value to products and services to drive a lot of profit while creating a lot of work opportunity for many people. The fact that a soft drink is 90% water but whose value increases significantly by combining various resources was interesting to me.

4 Material and Energy Balance

4.1 Material Balance

Material balance is an application of conservation of mass to the analysis of physical system. We calculate the materials entering and leaving the system, mass flows can be identified which might have been unknown or difficult to measure without this technique. The balance is calculated based on Pepsi it is the major product of the company and it is also the main brand of the company.

4.1.1 Balance on Pepsi Cola in Six Unit

Balance On Pepsi

Over All Mass Balance on Pepsi

Solid ingredients=37.9kg	DE= 15Kg
water=200Kg	water= 21,000Kg
Flavor=7.57Kg	Water= 4000K
Sugar= 6768Kg	

Known value: -

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mass of total water} &= 200 \text{ kg} + 4000 \text{ kg} + 21,000 \text{ kg} \\ &= 25,200 \text{ kg} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Mass of sugar} = 6768 \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Mass of Pepsi dry Component} = 37.9 \text{ kg}$$

But, Mass of CO₂ added in the soft drink is unknown and its percentage in 300ml of finished product is known, that is 3.6% CO₂ is present in 300ml (0.3l) of Pepsi. Let's calculate the mass of CO₂ based on the above information.

From 1 batch 3500 case beverage is produced. One case contains 24 bottles therefor from one Bach 24 *3500=84000 bottle of soft drink is produced and the volume of one bottle is 0.3l , so the total volume of one batch is 84000*0.3l =25,200l

$$\text{Volume of CO}_2 \text{ in } 0.3l = 0.3l * 3.6\% = 1.08l$$

$$\text{Volume of CO}_2 \text{ in } 25,200l = 25,200l * 1.08l / 0.3$$

$$= 907.2l$$

$$= 0.9072m^3$$

$$\text{Mass of CO}_2 = \text{density of CO}_2 * \text{volume of CO}_2$$

$$\text{Density of CO}_2 = 1.84kg/m^3$$

$$\text{Mass of CO}_2 = 1.84kg/m^3 * 0.9072m^3$$

$$= 1.669 \text{ kg}$$

$$\text{Mass of flavor} = 7.57kg$$

$$\text{Inlet Mass} = 25,200kg + 6768kg + 15kg + 37.9kg + 7.57kg + 1.669kg$$

$$= 32,028.47kg$$

Water balance: -

Let 'X' be mass fraction of the water component

$$X = 25,200kg / 32,028.47kg$$

$$= 0.787$$

Sugar balance: -

$$X = 6768kg / 32,028.47kg$$

$$= 0.2113$$

Pepsi dry Component balance: -

$$X = 37.9kg / 32,028.47kg$$

$$= 0.00119$$

Balance on flavor

$$X = 7.57\text{kg}/32,028.47\text{kg}$$

$$= 0.000236$$

4.1.2 Mass Balance for Mirinda Orange in Fourteen Unit

Given value;

Mass of water=3,220 kg

Mass of sugar=6,321 kg

M input=3,220 kg+6,321 kg

$$= 9,541 \text{ kg}$$

Water balance: -

$X = M \text{ total mass of water} / M \text{ total solution}$

$$X = 3,220 \text{ kg} / 9,541 \text{ kg} = 0.34\%$$

Sugar balance: -

$$X = 6,321 \text{ kg} / 9,541 \text{ kg} = 0.66\%$$

4.2 Energy Balance on Dissolving Tank

Energy is used to increase the solution of temperature from 25°C to 80°C

Water=1300kg

motor energy=4kw

sugar =2528.4 kg

Steam energy=?

DE = 15kg

$E_{in} = E_{stored} + E_{out}$ energy conservation

Assume ME and PE =0

$E=Q-W$; where Q and W are heat energy and motor energy respectively

$$Q = mcp\Delta T$$

$$=\sum mcp\Delta T$$

$$cp \text{ of water}=4.2\text{kJ/kg k}$$

$$cp \text{ of sugar}=1.24\text{kJ/kg k}$$

$$cp \text{ of DE}=5,95\text{J/kg k}$$

$$\text{Capacity of water} = 1,300\text{kg} * 4.2\text{kJ/kg k}$$

$$= 5,460\text{kJ/k}$$

$$=5,460,000\text{J/k}$$

$$\text{Capacity of sugar} =2,528.4\text{kg} * 1.24\text{kJ/kg k}$$

$$= 3,135.2\text{kJ/k}$$

$$=3,135,200\text{J/k}$$

Dissolving tank

$$\text{Capacity of DE}=595\text{J/kg k} *15\text{kg}$$

$$= 8925\text{J/k}$$

$$\sum cp \text{ mass} =\sum C$$

$$= 5,460,000\text{J/k} +3,135,200\text{J/k}+8,925\text{J/k}$$

$$= 8,604,125\text{J/k}$$

$$Q =\sum C (T_2-T_1)$$

$$= 8,604,125\text{J/K} (60)$$

$$= 516,247.500\text{kJ}$$

5 Case Study

5.1 List of problems observed at the company

In MoHA soft drinks industry Hawassa millennium Pepsi cola plant, I have observed many problems which can be solved. These problems makes workers less efficient at their work and costs the company a lot of money.

Some the problems I have observed are listed below:

- i. **High amount of water loss:-** through overflows and concentrated water(RO) .
- ii. **Manual dosing of sulfuric acid:-** There is no dosing pump for sulfuric acid in waste water treatment section, the acid is dosed manually which is extremely dangerous if it spills on the skin of workers who work in that section.
- iii. **Some parameters of quality checking are not measured:-** After treatment of waste water, instead of measuring all standard parameters like TDS, BOD,TSS and COD only PH and temperature of the water is measured and it is released to Chefe river. This is obviously really bad for the environment.
- iv. **Waste gases are released to the atmosphere:-** waste gases like SO_2 , SO_3 and other toxic gases which are byproducts of steam and carbon dioxide preparation section are released to the atmosphere without any treatment.
- v. **Some sections of the company are very hot:-** the temperature of syrup preparation section, bottle washer, boiler room and CO_2 preparation section is very high; especially at sunny afternoons it gates worse.
- vi. **The company uses imported beat/cane sugar:-** In the production process of soft drinks the company imports beat/cane sugar as beverage sweetener; which causes different health problems on the customers, and also it increases the cost of production of the company.
- vii. **Bad smell of the waste water treatment section:-** In the waste water treatment section there is bad smell rising from the effluent, which affects the health of the operator.
- viii. **In the filler bowl over fill and under fill occurs:-** under filled and over filled bottles occurs due to filler machine defects. Under fill is caused by damaged strader while overflow is caused by damaged rubber fill.

- ix. **Manual separation of under-filled and over-filled bottles:-** under filled and over filled bottles are removed from the packaging line by using man power. The bottles are inspected by visual inspection method which is less effective and tiresome.
- x. In our country there is high demand of sugar but there is no enough supply, so there is a shortage of sugar, besides the sugar used in the production of simple syrup have high calorie content which may cause obesity, diabetes, and heart disease, as well as poor dental health [16]. It also causes stroke and dementia [17].

5.2 List of solutions to the problems observed in the company

- i. Water is a precious resource and the company should try to use water more effectively.
- ii. Instead of manual dosing of sulfuric acid, a safe pumping system should be provided to avoid injury to workers.
- iii. All parameters of water quality test has to be strictly tested to avoid environmental pollution.
- iv. Waste gases should not be released to the environment. Instead it would be great if waste gases can be condensed and further processed for another use or for safe removal.
- v. For very hot sections of the company, it would be great to provide further cooling and heat conditioning for employee comfort and efficiency.
- vi. The bad smell coming from the water treatment facility should be avoided by providing some form of sealing to avoid escaping of bad odor to the environment.
- vii. To avoid overflow and under fill of bottles at the filler machine, a more frequent inspection, maintenance and operation to the machines has to be done.
- viii. The company uses imported cane sugar to sweeten its beverages. It would be great to use an artificial sweetener and further details for this solution has been presented on the next section.

5.3 Case Study: Replacement of Organic Sugar by Artificial sweeteners

The plant can produce healthier soft drinks while increasing its profit and productivity by using artificial sweeteners which have null calorie content and high sweetening capacity in combination with organic sugar.

The use of healthy artificial sweeteners can increase the company's profit by increasing the quality and healthiness of soft drinks and It also helps to decrease the calorie content of the soft drinks and it will minimize the cost of production.

5.3.1 Sugar Substitutes (artificial sweeteners)

Sugar substitutes as the name indicates are substitutes for organic sugars, like cane sugar for instance. These substitutes provide a sweet taste to foods as well as beverages while containing very less or no food energy hence they are called zero-calorie [4].

Artificial sweeteners can be made by processing plant extractions in an industry or by chemical synthesis. Most sugar substitutes are many times sweeter than sugar, that is, it takes very small amount of the sweeteners to produce the same level of sweetness [4][5].

Sugar substitutes are regulated as food additives in the United States of America by the Food and Drug administration (FDA). That means the FDA monitors the use of such sweeteners before they are used as a substitute in foods and drugs to make sure safety [5].

5.3.2 Sweeteners that are safe to use

Some sugar substitutes are “generally recognized as safe” (GRAS) according to the FDA. This means they don't need FDA approval because experts agreed based on a scientific data these products are safe to use in foods and beverages [5].

Sweeteners that are approved by the FDA and can be used as substitutes for sugar in the U.S. are:

- Acesulfame potassium (brand names: Sunett and Sweet One)
- Advantame
- Aspartame (two brand names: Equal and Nutrasweet)
- Neotame (brand name: Newtame)
- Saccharin (two brand names: Sweet 'N Low and Sweet Twin) and Sucralose (brand name: Splenda)

Aspartame (C₁₄H₁₈N₂O₅)

Aspartame is an artificial sweetener which is 200 times sweeter than sucrose, and is commonly used as a sugar substitute in foods and beverages. It is one of the most well researched food ingredient. Reviews by over 100 governmental regulatory bodies found the ingredient safe for consumption. Medical research studies have shown these sweeteners are safe for most people when used in moderation. [5][6].

Moreover, the National Cancer Institute in the U.S. stated that there is no evidence that show aspartame is carcinogenic.

Several clinical in 2018 from clinical experiments stated that the use of aspartame instead sugar effectively reduced body weight in adults and children because of reduced calorie intake [6].

Acesulfame potassium (C₄H₄KNO₄S)

Acesulfame is 200 times sweeter than sucrose just like aspartame. It is often blended with other sweeteners (usually sucralose or aspartame) to give a more sucrose-like taste by which the blend is sweeter than its components. In the European Union it is known by additive code E950 and it was discovered in 1967 by a German chemist Karl Clauss at Hoechst AG (now known as Nutrinova) [7].

Advantame (C₂₄H₃₀N₂O₇)

Advantame is a non-caloric artificial sweetener and it is about 20,000 times sweeter than sucrose and about 110 times sweeter than aspartame. Unlike other sweeteners, the FDA puts a limit on consumption of Advantame about 32.8 mg per kg of body weight.

However, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) makes more serious consumption limit for safety to 5 mg per Kg of body weight [7].

Neotame (C₂₀H₃₀N₂O₅)

Neotame, also known by Newtame, is another alternative for non-caloric artificial sweeteners and it has a similar chemical structure to aspartame. It is 8,000 sweeter than sucrose (sugar) [9].

Neotame enhances original food flavors, it can be used alone, but is often mixed with other sweeteners to increase their individual sweetness (i.e. synergistic effect) and decrease their off-flavors. It is relatively more stable than aspartame chemically [9].

It is suitable for use in carbonated soft drinks, yogurts, cakes, drink powders, bubble gums etc except meat and poultry. It can be used as a table top sweetener for hot drinks like coffee. It is also cost effective compared to other artificial sweeteners as it is required only in small amounts [10].

Saccharin (C₇H₅NO₃S)

Saccharin is an artificial sweetener with no food energy at all. It is around 300–400 times sweeter than sucrose. However, it has a bitter or metallic aftertaste, especially at high concentrations. Saccharin is used to sweeten products such as drinks, candies, cookies, and medicines [11].

5.3.3 Comparison and Summary of artificial sweeteners

Table 4: Summary and comparison of sweeteners

Sweetener name	Relative sweetness	Molar mass (g·mol ⁻¹)	Chemical formula	Color	Chemical structure
Aspartame	200X	294.307	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₅	White powder	
Acesulfame K	200X	201.242	C ₄ H ₄ KNO ₄ S	White powder	
Advantame	20,000X	458.511	C ₂₄ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₇	Yellow powder	
Neotame	8000X	378.469	C ₂₀ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₅	White powder	

Saccharin	300X to 400X	183.18	$C_7H_5NO_3S$	White solid	
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Though many resources on the internet claim side effects for the artificial sweeteners, there is no clear evidence that the artificial sweeteners are bad for health or cancer causing. But the most intense research and clinical trials indicate that artificial sweeteners are good for low or no calorie soft drinks as long as they are consumed on the suggested levels by the FDA as well as EFSA.

5.4 Methodology

In the process of replacing sugar by aspartame we use similar procedures with the preparation of simple syrup which passes through different unit operations. In order to produce zero calorie soft drinks, we use the following procedures.

- ✓ Calculate the amount of aspartame needed for one unit of the specific brand
- ✓ Calculate the favorable Temperature to dissolve aspartame in the dissolving tank and set the maximum temperature.
- ✓ Then test the theoretical procedure in laboratory scale by preparing sample product
- ✓ Evaluate the standard of the sample product weather it is at its expected standard or not
- ✓ If the sample product have good quality, it can be produced in large scale production, if not correction measures are applied.

5.4 Energy balance

Energy is used to increase the temperature from 25°C to 60°C .

Water=1,300kg

motor energy=4kw

Mass of aspartame =12.642kg

Steam energy=?

$$DE = 15\text{kg}$$

$$E_{\text{in}} = E_{\text{stored}} + E_{\text{out}}$$

Assume ME and PE = 0

$E = Q - W$; where Q and W are heat energy and motor energy respectively

$$Q = mcp\Delta T$$

$$= \sum mcp\Delta T$$

$$\text{cp of water} = 4.2\text{kJ/kg k}$$

$$\text{cp of aspartame} = 0.98\text{kJ/kg k}$$

$$\text{cp of DE} = 5.95\text{J/kg k}$$

$$\text{Capacity of water} = 1,300\text{kg} * 4.2\text{kJ/kg k}$$

$$= 5,460\text{kJ/k}$$

$$= 5,460,000\text{J/k}$$

$$\text{Capacity of sugar} = 2,528.4\text{kg} * 0.98\text{kJ/kg k}$$

$$= 2,477,832\text{J/k}$$

Dissolving tank

$$\text{Capacity of DE} = 5.95\text{J/kg k} * 15\text{kg}$$

$$= 8925\text{J/k}$$

$$\sum \text{cp mass} = \sum C$$

$$= 5,460,000\text{J/k} + 2,477,832\text{J/k} + 8,925\text{J/k}$$

$$= 7,946,757\text{J/k}$$

$$Q = \sum C (T_2 - T_1)k$$

$$= 7,946,757J (35)$$

$$=278,136.495KJ$$

5.5 Cost and energy analysis

5.5.1 Cost analysis

$$1\text{kg of sugar} = \$0.46$$

$$1\text{kg of aspartame} = \$14.8$$

Since aspartame is 200 times sweeter than sugar, one kilogram of aspartame can crate similar sweetness as two hundred kilograms of sugar.

$$1\text{kg of Aspartame} = 200\text{kg Sugar}$$

$$200\text{kg} * 0.46 = \$92$$

$$\text{Cost ratio of 200kg of sugar to 1kg of aspartame} = 92/14$$

$$= 6.6:1$$

One kilogram of aspartame is six times cheaper than 200kg of sugar, which is cost effective.

5.5.2 Energy analysis

The energy needed to dissolve aspartame is a lot smaller than the energy needed to dissolve sugar. Let's compare the heat energy (Q) balance done on the dissolving tank.

$$Q_{As} = 278,136.495KJ$$

$$Q_{su} = 516,247.500kJ$$

Let's calculate the difference ($Q_{Su} - Q_{As}$)

$$= 516,247.500kJ - 278,136.495kJ$$

$$= 238,111.005kJ$$

From the energy difference we can understand that aspartame requires smaller amount of heat energy when compared with the heat energy required by sugar.

5.6 Conclusions and recommendation on case study

5.6.1 Conclusion

According to my evaluation the overall organization of the plant, its food safety practice and quality assurance are very good. The company can increase its profit while increasing the quality and healthiness of the soft drinks by optimization of the input resources, particularly by the use of healthy artificial sweeteners.

Since artificial sweeteners are required in low amount, MoHA can partially replace the use of organic sugar by using artificial sweeteners. This has the following advantages

- The company will be able to produce low-energy soft drinks for customers who would like to enjoy the drinks without worrying about gaining weight.
- The company can increase its production capacity since it will no longer be limited by the availability of cane sugar which has been always facing shortage in our country.
- The company will also be able to introduce new varieties of the same product, such as zero-sugar soft drinks.

5.6.2 Recommendation

The case study indicates that using artificial sweeteners in the production of soft drinks results in a mutual benefit for the company and the customers. So it is recommended that the company should consider substituting organic sugar by aspartame.

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